

DESI Resumes Survey Operations After the Contreras Fire

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The Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument (DESI) on the 4m Mayall Telescope at Kitt Peak National Observatory is back on-sky after the Contreras Fire. Although operations at Kitt Peak are still not back to normal, the DESI survey observations have resumed.

Background Image: The Contreras Fire destroyed the poles carrying power lines to the mountain. The Tohono O'odham Utility Authority (TOUA) replaced 18 of these poles over miles of rugged, inaccessible terrain. The TOUA crews had to hike in and manually dig holes for the replacement poles. Given the lack of any vehicle access, the new poles were flown in by helicopter to the waiting TOUA crews. Power was restored to the observatory on 17 October 2022. *Credit: B. Stupak/NOIRLab*

DESI, a 5000-fiber multi-object spectrograph with a simultaneous circular three-degree field of view, saw first light on the Mayall in October 2020. After an initial period of commissioning and test observations, it began its five-year survey in May 2021. DESI briefly paused operations last summer to upgrade the focal plane control electronics, but was operating smoothly after it came back on-sky in September 2021. However, all operations at Kitt Peak had to be terminated and the mountaintop evacuated when the [Contreras Fire](#) began on 11 June 2022. DESI was shut down safely in advance of the evacuation. The fire was a serious threat to the summit and its many observatories, but thanks to heroic efforts by the fire crews and mountain staff, most of the facilities escaped nearly unscathed. Some smoke from the fire entered the Mayall enclosure, but the telescope and instrument were undamaged.

After numerous tests of the enclosure, telescope, and instrument, DESI resumed its mission on 10 September 2022. Line power was not restored to the summit until 17 October 2022. Prior to then, the Mayall was running on power from a diesel generator, which in turn was backed up by a second diesel generator. Since the wired internet connection to the mountain was also destroyed by the fire, the DESI and Mayall team have installed a temporary internet connection which provides low-bandwidth internet and allows the off-site members of the operations team to monitor the instrument and telescope telemetry. The transfer of data to Tucson and Berkeley, which used to happen automatically as data were taken, is now accomplished by writing the data to a hard disk and driving it to Tucson, where it is then uploaded to an internet-connected system for transfer. As a result of these ‘innovations’, DESI was back in action! Normal wired internet services were eventually restored on 07 December 2022, and DESI operations are now back to normal.

DESI’s and the Mayall’s five-year mission is to map the expansion history of the Universe over the last 10 billion years with unprecedented precision. It is doing so by obtaining redshift measurements for 40 million galaxies and quasars distributed over this large range in cosmic time. By measuring both the universal expansion and the time evolution of the clustering of galaxies, DESI will provide new, stronger constraints on our cosmological model and on the nature of dark energy. The DESI observations will result in the largest cosmic cartographic survey ever undertaken.

Despite the COVID-19 pandemic (which interrupted DESI commissioning and survey validation observations) and the Contreras Fire, DESI has proven itself a resilient and very efficient instrument. In only 300 nights of on-sky observations, DESI has already measured more than 15 million extragalactic source redshifts and obtained radial velocities for more than 4.7 million stars. The instrument is very efficient: the overhead time between exposures (which involves reading out the detectors while slewing the telescope, acquiring the new field, finding guide stars and initiating guiding, repositioning the fibers, and restarting the new exposure) is less than two minutes. The pipeline, which operates at Lawrence Berkeley Laboratory’s National Energy Research Scientific Computing Center (NERSC), delivers a catalog of redshifts from each night’s observations by the following morning. The high throughput of the system allows redshifts to be obtained for galaxies as faint as $r \sim 24$ AB mag. A recent pilot survey of the Andromeda Galaxy demonstrated that accurate radial velocities could be obtained for stars as faint as $z \sim 21.5$ AB mag.

The DESI Collaboration, an international group which involves nearly 1000 scientists and engineers distributed over 69 institutions, is hard at work analyzing the data and preparing the early DESI survey validation observations for an Early Data Release, scheduled for early 2023. The collaboration has recently submitted several papers describing the DESI target classes and the overall scope of the main surveys.

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